

MAGNETIC CONTROL OF LIGHT TRANSMISSION AND OF ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY IN (HYBRID) MAGNETORHEOLOGICAL SUSPENSIONS BASED ON BIOACTIVE COMPONENTS

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Abstract. Bio-magnetic active suspensions and tissues are manufactured from honey, cotton fibers and various concentrations of carbonyl iron (Φ_{CI}) microparticles. The obtained (h)MRSs composites are examined as magnetoactive materials for industrial and therapeutic applications. We propose a new experimental design, and show that the light transmission through (h)MRSs and the electrical conductivity are sensibly influenced by the intensity H and gradient δ of an external magnetic field, as well as by Φ_{CI} . These effects make (h)MRSs versatile candidates in fabrication of technical and medical devices and equipment which require a magnetic control of the light transmission and of the thermal transport of bioactive components. They can be used for various applications such as scaffolding biomaterials for tissue repair and regeneration or in the quality control of honey crystallization and of its derivative products in industrial processes.

Key words: Light transmittance, electrical conductivity, magnetorheological suspensions, bioactive components.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bio-magnetic suspensions and tissues consist from a bioactive matrix in which is dispersed a magnetizable phase and additives [1]. The matrix can be an organic liquid such as vegetable oil [2], honey (HB) [3, 4] etc., while the magnetizable phase usually consists from carbonyl iron (CI) microparticles [2, 3]. Although there are numerous applications of these types of materials such as in fabrication of structured magnetic circuits [5], electrical capacitors [6], magnetoresistors [7], in seismic protection [8] or in adaptive tuned vibration absorbers [9], an important issue affecting the physical performances of magnetorheological suspensions (MRSs) is the sedimentation of the magnetic phase.

In order to avoid this process, completely or partially, new research has shown the possibility of using environmentally-friendly and low-costs additives, such as turmeric microparticles [3], cotton fabrics [4], cellulose fibers [10], $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ or silsesquioxane nanoparticles [11, 12] etc. Thus, such materials can be used effectively in various medical therapies by exploiting the healing properties of the matrix, of the dispersed phases together with an external magnetic and electric field.

The aim of this work is to synthesize a new class of bio-active magnetorheological suspensions and to take advantage of a combined usage of the bioactive components from bio-magnetic suspensions together with the usage of magnetic and electric fields, so that to maximize the therapeutic effects of the obtained materials. Generally, improvements of these effects are achieved by eliminating the sedimentation process of the magnetizable phase, which leads to a more efficient selective release of the required bio-active components. Here, we reveal key properties which makes the bio-suspensions useful for incorporation into various smart textiles with phase change materials [13], into soft robotics [14] or, generally, into various devices for increasing the overall comfort of human beings [3].

For this purpose we use HB as a matrix since it contains more than 300 bio-active components [15, 16] which can be used for various therapies, by a selective transport. In addition, in order to have a good response in the presence of an external magnetic field as well as to avoid sedimentation processes, we use here CI as additives soaked in a cotton fiber tissue. Thus, by using a static magnetic field superimposed on an alternating electric field, specific bioactive components such as those required to fight against various pathogens [17, 18] can be selected by using the absorption characteristics of the alternating electric field [4]. To this aim, we make use of the "optical window" effect of living tissues [19], by which light with wavelengths between 650 and 1200 nm is allowed to penetrate enough deep through the skin so that, various useful photo-chemical reactions are initiated [20]. In this way the mechanisms underlying the photocatalytic degradation of some antibiotics, such as ciprofloxacin [21] or analgesics, such as antipyrine [22], from water systems by TiO_2 photocatalysis, can be elucidated.

Here, the control of light transmission through the bio-suspensions and tissues as well as the mass transport of the bioactive components is achieved by using a permanent magnet and a medium frequency electric field. In order to evaluate the therapeutic properties of the synthesized bio-suspensions we investigate here two types of samples: suspensions based on HB and CI microparticles (MRSs), and active bio-magnetic tissues (hMRSs) consisting from MRSs soaked into a tissue of cotton fibers. We show that very low volume fractions Φ_{CI} of CI microparticles, that is $\Phi_{\text{CI}} = 1 \text{ vol.}\%$, the transmission of white light increases up to 150 % in hMRSs, when the intensity of the external magnetic field increases up to $H_{\text{max}} = 46 \text{ kA/m}$. In addition, we show that the electrical conductivity for the same composition of

hMRSs increases up to 20 %, at the same value of the magnetic field intensity. Thus, it is demonstrated that the light transmission and electrical conductivity of the synthesized bioactive materials can be controlled in an external magnetic field. We explain qualitatively the observed effects by using the theory of magnetic dipolar approximation.

Generally, the obtained results can be used in fabrication of technical and medical devices and equipment aimed at the control quality of HB and its crystallization in industrial processes, as well as for performing selective and targeted release of various bioactive substances in the presence of a magnetic field. In the later case, it allows for performing specific photo-chemical reactions, useful for treatment of various skin-related diseases, such as eczema, psoriasis, varicose, hives etc., without involving any chemically synthesized substance harmful for human body.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for the synthesis of MRSs and hMRSs are the following:

- CI microparticles, in powder form, containing particles with diameters between 4.5 and 5.4 μm . The Fe content is higher than 97 % and the mass density of CI is $\rho_{\text{CI}} = 7.86 \text{ g/cm}^3$;
- HB with density of 1.40 g/cm^3 and viscosity $\eta_0 = 12 \text{ Pa} \times \text{s}$ at 297 K;
- Medical dressing (MD) consisting of cotton fiber, with granulation of 30 g/cm^2 .

The main steps followed in the fabrication of MRSs and hMRSs are the following:

1. One prepares two different mixtures S_1 and S_2 of CI and HB at about 330 K for about 300 s until one obtains a dark coloured suspension. The volumes and volume fractions of each component are listed in Tab. 1. Each mixture S_1 and S_2 is used further to prepare MRSs and hMRSs.
2. Four disks are cut from a projector foil (TS) and respectively from MD, as shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b) with diameters of 40 mm, and respectively 30 mm. On each of the TS disks are fixed two parallel copper electrodes with a diameter of $d_e = 0.28 \text{ mm}$ and situated at a distance $L = 5 \text{ mm}$, and are called support disks. On top of these support disks are superimposed MD disk, as shown in Fig. 1(c).
3. One pours into a mold a mixture of silicone rubber with catalyst. After polymerization one obtains the body shown in Fig. 2(a). The body is then mounted inside a toroidal coil together with the support disk, which is fixed at one opening.
4. From each sample S_1 and S_2 one extracts a volume of 0.70 cm^3 with the help of a syringe. This volume is then deposited on the support disk inside the silicone

Table 1

Composition of samples S_1 and S_2 used for synthesizing MRS and hMRS. V_{HB} and V_{CI} are the volumes of HB and respectively of CI. Φ_{HB} and Φ_{CI} are the volume fractions of HB and respectively of CI.

Sample	V_{HB} (cm ³)	V_{CI} (cm ³)	Φ_{HB} (vol.%)	Φ_{CI} (vol.%)
S_1	99.0	1.0	99.0	1.0
S_2	99.9	0.1	99.9	0.1

Fig. 1 – Photos of: (a) Transparent disk; Cotton fabric disk with thickness of 0.48 mm; (c) Configuration of cotton fibers (1), copper electrodes (2), and support-disks (3).

rubber body (Fig. 2(b)). Thus one obtains two MRSs with a diameter of 30 mm, thickness of about 1 mm, and composition given by S_1 , and respectively by S_2 .

5. On each of the support disks is deposited another volume of 0.7 cm³ of S_1 and respectively S_2 , together with the MD disk. At the end of this procedure one obtains two hMRSs with the same dimensions as of MRSs obtained in previous step, and with the same composition given by S_1 , and respectively by S_2 .

A photo of the experimental setup used for investigating the light transmission and electrical conductivity of MRSs and hMRSs in a magnetic field is shown in Fig. 3(a), while the overall configuration is shown in Fig. 3(b).

The setup consists from a toroidal coil electrically connected to a power source. Inside the coil are fixed by turn the disks with MRSs, and respectively with hMRSs by means of the silicone rubber sleeves. Also, by using the same sleeves, a digital microscope and a luxmeter probe are fixed to the coil. The electrical conductors of the disks with MRSs and hMRSs pass through the sleeves and are connected to an RLC bridge.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The digital microscope generates white light which is incident to the (h)MRSs disks. The microscope is connected to a computing unit with 4 GB of RAM, containing a preinstalled software with which (h)MRSs can be visualized and stored on

Fig. 2 – (a) Silicone rubber body. (b) Silicone rubber body together with the magnetic field generator coil. 1 - toroidal coil, 2 - silicone rubber body (the same as in a), 3 - bioactive magnetic suspension/tissue on a transparent support.

Fig. 3 – (Color online). Experimental setup: (a) Photo, 1 - toroidal coil, 2 - digital microscope, 3 - probe, 4 - luxmeter, 5 - Gaussmeter, 6 - computing unit (CU); (b) Overall configuration: WLG - digital microscope, CU - computing unit, TC - toroidal coil, DC - continuous current source, LX - luxmeter, LM - luxmeter probe, MT - (h)MRSs, R - inner radius of the toroidal coil, Br - RLC bridge, Oxy - Cartesian coordinate system, δ - magnetic field intensity gradient vector, H magnetic field intensity vector.

a magnetic disk. Figure 4 shows photos of hMRSs without and with an external magnetic field at $H = 25$ kA/m. It is clear that the light transmission is greatly determined whether the (h)MRSs is under the influence of a magnetic field. Without a magnetic field (Fig. 4(a)), CI microparticles are randomly distributed throughout the (h)MRSs, thus reducing from the illuminance passing through the disks. However, when a magnetic field is applied, CI microparticles form chain-like aggregates oriented along the magnetic field lines, thus allowing the illuminance to increase. For the investigated (h)MRSs, when the magnetic field is turned off, the CI return to their initial state characterized by a random distribution on the disk's surface.

Fig. 4 – (Color online). Digital microscopy of hMRSs without (a) and with (b) magnetic field ($H = 25$ kA/m). Without a magnetic field, CI microparticles are randomly distributed, while in a magnetic field, they form chain-like aggregates oriented along the field lines. The semitransparent rectangular grids with larger edge size of about 3 mm is the cotton fiber.

Investigations concerning the influence of magnetic field on the electrical conductivity and light transmission through (h)MRSs using white light is performed in three main steps.

3.1. INFLUENCE OF MAGNETIC FIELD IN THE PROXIMITY OF (H)MRSS

By using the Gaussmeter probe one measures along O_x and O_y axis (see Fig. 3(b)) the magnetic field intensity H generated by the toroidal coil, when the current intensity through the coil is $I = 1.22$ A_{dc}. Along the coil diameter and the O_y axis, H is not constant. At $R = 15$ nm from the coil center, H increases by about 9.09 %, and thus a gradient δ of magnetic field is established along O_y axis. Variation of δ with intensity I is shown in Fig. 5 (black dots). However, along the thickness $d \simeq 1$ mm of (h)MRSs (O_x axis in Fig. 3(b)), H is constant, and its values depend on intensity I , as shown in Fig. 5 (red dots).

3.2. ILLUMINANCE PRODUCED BY PASSING WHITE LIGHT THROUGH TS, MD AND SUPPORT DISKS

The transparent disk TS from Fig. 1(a) plays the role of support for both MRS and hMRS. In order to reveal the influence of disks without (h)MRSs on the illuminance, we proceed as follows: first, one measures the illuminance produced by the microscope source of white light, without the presence of disks. The obtained value is $E_0 = 782$ lx. Second, the distances between light sources and disk, as well as the distance between disk and luxmeter probe are fixed. Finally, we introduce by turn, inside the toroidal coil, first TS and then MD disks. The recorded values of illuminances are $E_1 = 742$ lx, and respectively $E_2 = 328$ lx.

Fig. 5 – (Color online). Variation of magnetic field intensity (H) and gradient δ with intensity I of the electrical current through the toroidal coil.

3.3. ILLUMINANCE AND RESISTANCE OF (H)MRSS IN A MAGNETIC FIELD

The influence of magnetic field on light transmission and electrical conductivity of (h)MRSs is investigated as follows: first, one fixes by turn, transparent disks with MRSs, and respectively with hMRSs in the center of the toroidal coil. For fixed values I of the electric current passing through the coil, one measures every second the illuminance E and resistance \mathcal{R} for a total time of 300 s.

The obtained values are presented in Figs. 6 and 7 (discrete dots), and show that MRSs and hMRSs are translucent, and respectively, electrically conductive. Note that in both figures, E , and respectively \mathcal{R} are represented as a function of intensity I passing through the coil. In this way we include the effects of both magnetic field intensity H and its gradient δ , since they also depend on I , as shown in Fig. 5. In particular, for $I = 0$, *i.e.* $H = 0$ and $\delta = 0$ in Fig. 5 one can observe that both the light transmission and electrical conductivity of (h)MRSs are sensibly influenced by the volume fraction Φ_{CI} of CI microparticles.

While in the case of MRSs, E increases by a factor of about 1.25, when decreasing Φ_{CI} from 1 vol.% to 0.1 vol.%, in the case of hMRSs the increase is about ten times larger. Note from Fig. 5 that at $H \neq 0$ and $\delta \neq 0$, *i.e.* $I \neq 0$, the magnetic field has a more pronounced increase with I , as compared with the gradient. This shows that at $I \neq 0$, both H and δ contribute to E and respectively to \mathcal{R} . However, their relative contribution changes with increasing I : while at $I \simeq 0$, E and \mathcal{R} have an approximate equal contribution, at $I \simeq 1.2 A_{dc}$, H has a contribution about 4 times larger than that of δ . For fixed values of Φ_{CI} , E of MRSs increases by a factor of maxim 1.32 when decreasing Φ_{CI} from 1 vol.% to 0.1 vol.%, and which corresponds to $I \simeq 1.2 A_{dc}$, while for hMRSs, E still increases by a factor of about 10.

Fig. 6 – (Color online). Variation of illuminance E for MRSs and hMRSs with intensity I of the electrical current through the toroidal coil. S_1 contains $\Phi_{CI} = 1. \text{ vol.}\%$ CI, and S_2 contains $\Phi_{CI} = 0.1 \text{ vol.}\%$ CI (see Tab. 1). Dots - experimental data, continuous lines - theoretical fit using Eq. (17). Note that hMRSs allows less light to pass than MRSs due to the presence of the MD, which plays the role of an absorbent.

Fig. 7 – (Color online). Variation of resistance \mathcal{R} for MRSs and hMRSs with intensity I of the electrical current through the toroidal coil. Dots - experimental data, continuous lines - theoretical fit using Eq. (16).

A similar behaviour can be seen also for the resistance of MRSs and hMRSs shown in Fig. 7, where at $I = 0$ a decrease of Φ_{CI} from 1 vol.% to 0.1 vol.% leads to a decrease of resistance by a factor of about 1.54 for MRSs, and by a factor of 2.1 for hMRSs. At constant Φ_{CI} , \mathcal{R} has a quasi-constant behaviour up to $I \simeq 0.85 \text{ A}_{dc}$ for both MRSs and hMRSs. At higher values, \mathcal{R} starts to decrease more pronounced. This behaviour can be explained also through the interplay between various contributions of H and δ , when increasing the current intensity I through the coil.

Fig. 8 – (Color online). Variation of relative illuminance α (Eq. (1)) for MRSs (a) and hMRSs (b) with intensity I of the electrical current through the toroidal coil.

3.4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The results obtained in Fig. 6 clearly shows that the light emitted by the transmitter, and recorded by the luxmeter probe, depends on the structure of the (h)MRSs, through the value of volume fraction Φ_{CI} , as well as on the external magnetic field. For a quantitative characterization of the translucence of (h)MRSs, we introduce the relative illuminance through:

$$\alpha(\%) = \left(\frac{E}{E_0} - 1 \right) \times 100, \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is the illuminance in the absence of magnetic field, and E is the illuminance in the presence of a magnetic field. By using the values of illuminances from Fig. 6(a) and (b) in Eq. (1) one obtains the relative illuminance $\alpha(\%)$ as a function of intensity I for MRSs and hMRSs, as shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b). The results show that the relative illuminance depends on Φ_{CI} , and is sensibly influence by the composition of the biomaterial. The same figure shows that α also increases with intensity I . For MRSs, α decreases by a factor of about 1.4 when Φ_{CI} is increased from 0.1 vol.% to 1 vol.%. However, in the case of hMRSs (Fig. 8(b)), α increases by a factor of about 10 at $I = 1.2 \text{ A}_{dc}$. This effect arise since for hMRSs, $E_0 \simeq 182 \text{ lx}$ at $\Phi_{CI} = 0.1 \text{ vol.}\%$, which is much higher as compared to $E_0 \simeq 17 \text{ lx}$ at $\Phi_{CI} = 1 \text{ vol.}\%$.

As in the case of illuminance, in order to compare the variation of R with intensity I for MRSs and hMRSs, we introduce the relative resistance, defined by:

$$\beta(\%) = \left(\frac{\mathcal{R}}{\mathcal{R}_0} - 1 \right) \times 100, \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{R}_0 is the resistance without a magnetic field, and \mathcal{R} is the resistance in the presence of the magnetic field.

The quantities \mathcal{R} and \mathcal{R}_0 from Fig. 7 are introduced in Eq. (2), and one obtains

Fig. 9 – (Color online). Variation of relative resistance β (Eq. (2)) for MRSs (a) and hMRSs (b) with intensity I of the electrical current through the toroidal coil.

the variation of relative resistance β with intensity I of the electric current through the coil, as shown in Fig. 9. The results show that the electrical resistance of biomaterials decreases in the magnetic field produced by the coil. The quantity β increases in absolute value with increasing the volume fraction Φ_{CI} , and respectively, with increasing the intensity I .

3.5. THEORETICAL MODELS FOR RESISTANCE AND ILLUMINANCE

The results presented in Figs. 8 and 9 suggest that important correlations arise between the optical and electrical phenomena occurring in these materials. In order to characterize them quantitatively, we make several assumptions: first, CI microparticles are identical, second, and their size is equal to the average diameter $d_m = 5 \mu\text{m}$, and third, in the presence of a magnetic field, CI microparticles are transformed into magnetic dipoles. Therefore the magnetic moment of the microparticles, projected along Or-axis attached to the radius R (see Fig. 8) can be calculated according to [23]:

$$m \equiv \frac{\pi}{6} \chi d_m^3 H = 0.5\pi d_m^3 H, \quad (3)$$

where χ is the initial magnetic susceptibility, and H is the magnetic field intensity. The quantity χ can be obtained from [23]:

$$\chi = 3 \frac{\mu_{CI} - \mu_{HB}}{\mu_{CI} + \mu_{HB}} \simeq 3, \quad (4)$$

when $\mu_{CI} \gg \mu_{HB}$. Here, μ_{CI} and μ_{HB} are the magnetic permeabilities of CI microparticles, and respectively of HB, or HB soaked with cotton fibers.

On the surface of (h)MRSs, the magnetic field gradient vector δ has a radial distribution, as shown in Fig. 10. In the presence of a magnetic field gradient arise magnetic interactions between two neighboring magnetic dipoles. Their intensity

Fig. 10 – (Color online). A model of (h)MRSs in a magnetic field: (a) Front view. (b) Cross-section. R - radius, δ - magnetic field gradient vector. H - magnetic field intensity vector.

along the radius R , is given by:

$$\mathbf{F}_m \equiv -\mu_0\mu_{\text{HB}}m\boldsymbol{\delta} = -0.5\pi\mu_0\mu_{\text{HB}}d_m^3H\boldsymbol{\delta}, \quad (5)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability. The resistance force arising from the embedding matrix is given by [23]:

$$\mathbf{F}_\eta = 3\pi\eta d_m \mathbf{v}, \quad (6)$$

where η is the apparent viscosity of (h)MRSs, and \mathbf{v} is the velocity vector. In a magnetic field, when the two forces are at equilibrium, inside the matrix are formed magnetic dipole chains, as shown in Fig. 4. The ends of these chains are attached to the copper electrodes used in the second step of Sec. II. B for preparation of active biosuspensions and tissues (see also Fig. 1c).

Therefore, a contact electrical resistance is established between the dipoles from the chain. In order to obtain a mathematical expression of this resistance we assimilate the resistor to a linear one. Thus, by using the formula which gives the expression for the contact electrical resistance between two magnetic dipoles, we can write, the well know expression:

$$\mathcal{R}_r = \frac{4r}{\sigma_0 d_m^2}, \quad (7)$$

where r is the distances between the center of masses of dipoles, and σ_0 is the electrical conductivity of MRS/hMRSs without magnetic field.

By using the equilibrium condition for the forces \mathbf{F}_m and \mathbf{F}_η , projected on

Or-axis (see Fig. 10) one obtains the equation of motion of the dipoles, that is:

$$3\pi\eta\frac{dr}{dt} + 0.5\pi\mu_0\mu_{HB}d_m^2H\delta = 0. \quad (8)$$

At the initial moment when the magnetic field is applied, the distance between the center of masses of the magnetic dipoles is [24]:

$$r = r_0 = \frac{d_m}{\sqrt[3]{\Phi_{CI}}} = \begin{cases} 23.02 \mu m & \text{for } S_1 \\ 50.00 \mu m & \text{for } S_2. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

However, at $t > 0$, for both S_1 and S_2 , the distance between the center-of-masses of the dipoles is r , and therefore Eq. (8) can be rewritten as:

$$r = r_0 \left(1 - \frac{\mu_0\mu_{HB}d_m^2H\delta t}{6\eta r_0} \right). \quad (10)$$

Along "Or" direction the maximum number of contact electrical resistances is:

$$n_r = \frac{R}{2d_m}, \text{ when } n_r \gg 1. \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the resistance of a dipole chain of length R , is obtained from Eqs. (7), (10) and (11), and it has the expression:

$$\mathcal{R}_r \equiv n_r \mathcal{R}_r = \frac{2R}{\sigma_0 d_m^3} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_0\mu_{HB}d_m^2H\delta t}{6\eta r_0} \right). \quad (12)$$

Along the thickness d of (h)MRSs, the number of magnetic dipoles can be approximated by:

$$n \equiv \frac{\Phi_{CI}V}{V_p} = \frac{6\Phi_{CI}R^2d}{\pi d_m^3}, \quad (13)$$

where V is the volume of (h)MRSs, and V_p is the volume of the average dipole. Then, the number of dipole chains from the (h)MRSs volume can be approximated by:

$$n_l = \frac{n}{n_r} = \frac{6\Phi_{CI}Rd}{\pi d_m^2}, \quad (14)$$

and therefore the electrical resistance along R is:

$$\mathcal{R} \equiv \frac{\mathcal{R}_R}{n_l} = \mathcal{R}_0 \left(1 - \frac{\mu_0\mu_{HB}d_m^2H\delta t}{6\eta r_0} \right), \quad (15)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_0 = \pi r_0 / (3\sigma_0 d_m \Phi_{CI} d)$ is the electrical resistance in the absence of the magnetic field (see also Eq. (2)).

Equation (15) shows that for fixed values of time t , the resistance \mathcal{R} depends on the product between magnetic field intensity H and its gradients δ . We also saw in Fig. 5 that both H and δ depend on the intensity I of the electric current passing

through the coil. These observations suggest us that Eq. (15) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_0 (1 - kI^2), \quad (16)$$

where k is a coupling constant, with units of A^{-2} . Thus, we can use this relation to fit the experimental data for the resistance \mathcal{R} . Figure 7 shows the corresponding fits as continuous lines for (h)MRSs, with S_1 and S_2 . The values of the parameters \mathcal{R}_0 , E_0 and k are listed in Tab. 2, and respectively in Tab. 3. The same figure shows that the approximation between the theoretical model and experimental data is very good. This suggests that the proposed model describes well the underlying current flow in (h)MRSs.

In the presence of a magnetic field, the ordering of the magnetisable phase in the form of chain-like aggregates, and their displacements towards the edges of the toroidal coil (Fig. 10), together with the results from Figs. 6 and 7 suggest that the relationship between the emergent light from (h)MRSs and the magnetic field is similar to the one characterizing the electrical resistance. Thus, we can write:

$$E = E_0 + (1 + kI^2), \quad (17)$$

where E_0 is the illuminance produced without the presence of magnetic field. The corresponding fits are shown also by continuous lines in Fig. 6, where we can see that, as in the case of resistance, the agreement between the experimental data and the theoretical model is very good. This suggests that the proposed model can adequately characterize the light-diffusion processes occurring in (h)MRSs.

Table 2

The parameters used in Eqs. (16) and (17) to fit experimental data in Fig. 7, and respectively in Fig. 6 for MRSs.

Sample	\mathcal{R}_0 (M Ω)	E_0 (lx)	k (A $^{-2}$)
S_1	0.86	325	0.052
S_2	0.56	410	0.075

Table 3

The parameters used in Eqs. (16) and (17) to fit experimental data in Fig. 7, and respectively in Fig. 6 for hMRSs.

Sample	\mathcal{R}_0 (M Ω)	E_0 (lx)	k (A $^{-2}$)
S_1	2.30	30	0.145
S_2	1.10	189	0.080

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have successfully synthesized two types of bioactive membranes. First type is based on MRSs consisting of HB and CI microparticles, and the second one is based on hMRSs consisting of HB and CI microparticles soaked into a cotton fabric tissue. The obtained membranes have a thickness of about 1 mm and lateral dimensions of about 30 mm, and are used as magnetoactive materials between the poles of an electromagnet.

We build and describe an experimental setup for measuring the effect of an external magnetic field generated by the toroidal coil of the electromagnet, on the resistance and illuminance of (h)MRSs at various concentrations of CI microparticles Φ_{CI} .

The results show the formation inside (h)MRSs of magnetic dipoles in the presence of the magnetic field, which are arranged in the form of chain-like aggregates. The effect of the magnetic field on the electrical resistance and light transmission through (h)MRSs in white-light is explained by the decrease of the distance between magnetic dipoles with increasing magnetic field intensity. This, in turn, leads to a decrease of the electrical resistance (Fig. 7) and to an increase of light transmission (Fig. 6). We explain the results in the framework of dipolar approximation and show that they can be successfully applied in fabrication of various bio-medical and industrial equipment devices where a selective and targeted release of bio-active components is required, in the presence of an external magnetic field, or for the quality control and crystallization of HB and of its derivatives in industrial processes.

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REFERENCES

1. I. Bica, Rom. J. Phys. **63**, 704 (2018).
2. S. Kolekar, R. V. Kurahatti, V. G. Kamble, S.-B. Choi, Intern. J. Nanosci. **18**, 1850041 (2019).
3. I. Bica, E. M. Anitas, J. Ind. Eng. Chem. **64**, 276–283 (2018).
4. I. Bica, E. M. Anitas, Mater. & Des. **155**, 317–324 (2018).
5. Z. Strecker, M. Kubík, P. Víttek, J. Roupec, D. Paloušek, V. Šreibr, Smart Mater. Struct. **28**(5), 055016 (2019).
6. L. M. Cirtina, I. Bica, L. Chirigiu, D. Cirtina, Rom. Rep. Phys. **71**, 509 (2019).
7. I. Bica, E. M. Anitas, Rom. Rep. Phys. **72**, 501 (2020).
8. M. D. Christie, S. Sun, L. Deng, D. H. Ning, H. Du, S. W. Zhang, W. H. Li, Mech. Syst. Sign. Process. **116**, 530–544 (2019).
9. G. N. Susheelkumar, S. M. Murigendrappa, K. V. Gangadharan, Mech. Syst. Sign. Process. **116**, 530–544 (2019).

10. D. H. Bae, H. J. Choi, K. Choi, J. D. Nam, Md. S. Islam, N. Kao, *Coll. Surf. A* **514**, 161–167 (2017).
11. I. Bica, E. M. Anitas, Q. Lu, H. J. Choi, *Smart Mater. Struct.* **27**, 095021 (2018).
12. A. Noureddine, C. J. Brinker, *Chem. Eng. J.* **340**, 125–147 (2018).
13. Y. Lu, X. Xiao, J. Fu, C. Huan, S. Qi, Y. Zhan, Y. Zhu, G. Xu, *Chem. Eng. J.* **355**, 532–539 (2019).
14. M. Cianchetti, C. Laschi, A. Menciassi, P. Dario, *Nature Rev. Mater.* **3**, 143–153 (2018).
15. P. V. Rao, K. T. Krishnan, N. Salleh, S. H. Gan, *Rev. Bras. Farmacog.* **26**, 657–664 (2016).
16. A. Lal, K. Chohan, A. Chohan, A. Chakravarti, *Clinical Otolaryngology* **42**(3), 651–660 (2017).
17. D. F. Williams, *Biomaterials* **29**, 2941–2953 (2008).
18. D. Campoccia, L. Montanaro, C. R. Arciola, *Biomaterials* **34**, 8018–8029 (2013).
19. Y. Y. Huang, A. C. H. Chen, J. D. Carroll, M. R. Hamblin, *Dose-Response* **7**, 353–383 (2009).
20. J. Hu, Y. Chen, Y. Li, Z. Zhou, Y. Cheng, *Biomaterials* **112**, 133–140 (2017).
21. X. Hu, X. Hu, Q. Peng, L. Zhou, X. Tan, L. Jiang, C. Tang, H. Wang, S. Liu, Y. Wang, Z. Ning, *Chem. Eng. J.* **380**, 122366 (2020).
22. J. M. Monteagudo, A. Duran, M. R. Martinez, I. San Martín, *Chem. Eng. J.* **380**, 122410 (2020).
23. P. Domínguez-García, S. Melle, J. M. Pastor, M. A. Rubio, *Phys. Rev. E* **76**, 051403 (2007).
24. T. B. Jones "*Electromechanics of Particles*", (Cambridge University Press, 1995).